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Genome Sequencing and Analysis Facility Jobs

Job Information for JA20267

Sequencing Data

Sequencing run SA20189

Data delivery for Job JA20267 in Run SA20189 uses BaseSpace.

Select this link to login to BaseSpace. Please see this page for more information.

MultiQC report not available.

File (click for FastQC report if available)	# of reads	md5sum
SG100_S152_L002_R1_001.fastq.gz	3313059	13e060ffa95a73a8916f90bc4d5b5701
SG101_S156_L001_R1_001.fastq.gz	2880215	347aca3583d48821d6a88685cb164885
SG101_S156_L002_R1_001.fastq.gz	2838542	f4828505ab14bb0295935e50048e87d5
SG102_S160_L001_R1_001.fastq.gz	2549185	13ac5861ac3f6441901c78289899c11a
SG102_S160_L002_R1_001.fastq.gz	2524786	9232ec627d0be48f975a6a89a4b2dacb
SG103_S164_L001_R1_001.fastq.gz	2718008	688b46ee5c3bfbf1fcb2cd5a7c18bc73
SG103_S164_L002_R1_001.fastq.gz	2670329	70b32bd1033e144f4855696075e8e63e
SG104_S168_L001_R1_001.fastq.gz	2780615	33b4489f3e1e23f95219bd717b3b1549
SG104_S168_L002_R1_001.fastq.gz	2754322	ee064067b2e04fb84dce1d4ff7eab273
SG105_S172_L001_R1_001.fastq.gz	2994130	2d7aa6f3474e386e061215a6ba616c9f

SG105_S172_L002_R1_001.fastq.gz	2942153	ec23d293181b491fae750470cced03cd
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SG106_S176_L002_R1_001.fastq.gz	4924790	94ca4b37e30cbb78b6258f6d253fd457
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SG108_S183_L002_R1_001.fastq.gz	2990099	3802f4d3c48a960637f70b6ee42608af
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SG128_S170_L002_R1_001.fastq.gz	3289848	8fd76d2e01e6b7758d5d811f991b0ecf
SG129_S174_L001_R1_001.fastq.gz	2882718	899c0818551c03ed3688d0a13dad9e34
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SG142_S179_L002_R1_001.fastq.gz	2507961	1cdb6afa1e9a764a804033997be40b27
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SG33_S110_L001_R1_001.fastq.gz	3402984	a2905e86933171ad6081d100f0c2e0b0
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SG37_S48_L002_R1_001.fastq.gz	4320185	b8b7ed85a220cd85d51be391c171e4df
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SG39_S64_L001_R1_001.fastq.gz	3637987	7015dd5dc9fce9429aa577aa087f762f
SG39_S64_L002_R1_001.fastq.gz	3631810	20437b0cdc18b70399e2241a6d5b427b
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SG42_S88_L001_R1_001.fastq.gz	3358373	313b4dbf4af488315c6029195f6ebcb7
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SG4_S69_L001_R1_001.fastq.gz	3092692	d1f6550ddf803aa653ba3b2d94b90614
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SG53_S81_L002_R1_001.fastq.gz	4264503	1c44392067ce9462ecf91209ba393394
SG54_S89_L001_R1_001.fastq.gz	3609539	29f0ae774d550c89265fb226d3a58c6d
SG54_S89_L002_R1_001.fastq.gz	3599467	26231cd53d1bac4b708f3af9d90d705c
SG55_S97_L001_R1_001.fastq.gz	3701586	aad6f6c7979842981989878c98c37f28
SG55_S97_L002_R1_001.fastq.gz	3642072	47c6a886826d9107130763c2794c5e5f
SG56_S105_L001_R1_001.fastq.gz	4136781	2ccd2f3c9b87e0bed8b10614cfc647c7
SG56_S105_L002_R1_001.fastq.gz	4110118	8d343b1e9bd9b9f783e3ea75af8ae3f6
SG57_S112_L001_R1_001.fastq.gz	3998424	697f3b4fb625772042fecfa783842c724
SG57_S112_L002_R1_001.fastq.gz	3982468	76660edd0b9c3380a9a9db07d1ac7593
SG58_S120_L001_R1_001.fastq.gz	3418716	75f03df85912f7447410d1541dd715b8
SG58_S120_L002_R1_001.fastq.gz	3412593	afc4af9ad95126bc3e361ed41777d081
SG59_S128_L001_R1_001.fastq.gz	2904501	8b47975ef19ddd1485428f6d087d70c1
SG59_S128_L002_R1_001.fastq.gz	2891522	420262825a982d948d2ae840dd99bfe4
SG5_S77_L001_R1_001.fastq.gz	3859346	af734251d560eb1140a751af4fc02a52
SG5_S77_L002_R1_001.fastq.gz	3834268	b74f48257e468f857545cfaafa16be40
SG60_S136_L001_R1_001.fastq.gz	3256974	08fd269fb004eea06bbefda6f5e68a85
SG60_S136_L002_R1_001.fastq.gz	3238203	cf35e1ab25db5b0d0122ce5b6392c26b
SG61_S50_L001_R1_001.fastq.gz	4204036	2ff356ab9b491648a22f1ee62be907f2
SG61_S50_L002_R1_001.fastq.gz	4202691	47fec58940b9e1f8133f64b56f3a2692
SG62_S58_L001_R1_001.fastq.gz	4293960	6dd1421f5a43b8ff57866af07339b6cc
SG62_S58_L002_R1_001.fastq.gz	4297146	f20d40e8cca817729b30d655fcf4b87b
SG63_S66_L001_R1_001.fastq.gz	4857100	ae565f014a1868907ddda4d22ef5a074
SG63_S66_L002_R1_001.fastq.gz	4857028	bcc1efd496e33d0c3de5a0d4c814dfd4
SG64_S74_L001_R1_001.fastq.gz	3506223	ca5b4c96e761d5796389d474306cb93b
SG64_S74_L002_R1_001.fastq.gz	3500361	92f674d386c1c9fb26f4598019c23a19
SG65_S82_L001_R1_001.fastq.gz	4143092	049dece5b969aa49fa888855bce979cf

SG65_S82_L002_R1_001.fastq.gz	4136873	6c8ac5dacc89caa47e9d8be766f780c6
SG66_S90_L001_R1_001.fastq.gz	3328575	d69fea332ef4ae7e04ce03bce3c2ab3b
SG66_S90_L002_R1_001.fastq.gz	3302551	382a5c36313b7faa0b84e21d4f68989f
SG67_S98_L001_R1_001.fastq.gz	3518102	6156e4ebd0f1e5775cd30bd70c15539a
SG67_S98_L002_R1_001.fastq.gz	3517864	3a327d57c1015541887e411ab12cd642
SG68_S106_L001_R1_001.fastq.gz	4446897	4204790257f084a44da10c2da704016e
SG68_S106_L002_R1_001.fastq.gz	4438488	d8ed276f21a2871c6217a68e853c32e3
SG69_S113_L001_R1_001.fastq.gz	3769717	75e24ce68e203ebed2e8ae4cce9f8926
SG69_S113_L002_R1_001.fastq.gz	3756581	4a02219f957bc29a7e157f710111c5a8
SG6_S85_L001_R1_001.fastq.gz	3299447	354405c17c5174e7b54cbf3c97ec050f
SG6_S85_L002_R1_001.fastq.gz	3282590	e7866060f9cb34293f0685f8090e4a32
SG70_S121_L001_R1_001.fastq.gz	3622662	349294bf49e8ff70fa041c0db29ffa33
SG70_S121_L002_R1_001.fastq.gz	3627891	97d2865ac06ca01e8209f559d1e0d35d
SG71_S129_L001_R1_001.fastq.gz	2917573	1d219d4ed2c9a6589eb52b75b481ac86
SG71_S129_L002_R1_001.fastq.gz	2902853	22ca3dadce8148750fd19cfe4efb5914
SG72_S137_L001_R1_001.fastq.gz	3302980	25e5af7125895b33b351456e0ea1fd6a
SG72_S137_L002_R1_001.fastq.gz	3284329	2e3769b02fbd90c27779c22154253c16
SG73_S51_L001_R1_001.fastq.gz	3270387	47ed186b45c805c7280d661555d4d01a
SG73_S51_L002_R1_001.fastq.gz	3258785	73a043d8624837143cf851f5d18e386b
SG74_S59_L001_R1_001.fastq.gz	3024778	1c844d5de8da29f9574d0367fec5657b
SG74_S59_L002_R1_001.fastq.gz	3017090	c6e09abcca13ef0fb3b01648611cde79
SG75_S67_L001_R1_001.fastq.gz	2953438	dc550800d7e7996c42c14bda427759a3
SG75_S67_L002_R1_001.fastq.gz	2947775	902489f3de887fcb00fdd34cfc06939
SG76_S75_L001_R1_001.fastq.gz	3173237	20a3cf2957b182007d8c402359bf124a
SG76_S75_L002_R1_001.fastq.gz	3176516	2dff8d2249a89deef8cbd5c1d4d56f73
SG77_S83_L001_R1_001.fastq.gz	3193769	aaf144df9fa5e8a40a4c3641ce0c416d
SG77_S83_L002_R1_001.fastq.gz	3179184	c3f76e9a994915d17b96b38c348c2782
SG78_S91_L001_R1_001.fastq.gz	2595490	8a3883aeafc0744e81a0a44392b41f94

SG78_S91_L002_R1_001.fastq.gz	2579786	3fc201daf3bd2458fd552d5258d3da9b
SG79_S99_L001_R1_001.fastq.gz	2540398	3ad94a45d63c4c42de535962d3d19d36
SG79_S99_L002_R1_001.fastq.gz	2527260	4deee5076cbd1ae27f8b576794943c93
SG7_S93_L001_R1_001.fastq.gz	3632886	fc417ba6b5f15d368b45c069a310a1fc
SG7_S93_L002_R1_001.fastq.gz	3625183	7f3df6e505d6a4f3827aed7540b042b8
SG80_S107_L001_R1_001.fastq.gz	2616639	b2a0f30e2233ea15621fe5ffdbede431
SG80_S107_L002_R1_001.fastq.gz	2598949	4a347f2414df295cb9363346ddcf5c4b
SG81_S114_L001_R1_001.fastq.gz	2695758	8133b2ef8b9530bd4b2f4931e371c345
SG81_S114_L002_R1_001.fastq.gz	2687298	3faa96e490a3f170cedde1b0da2121a9
SG82_S122_L001_R1_001.fastq.gz	2846245	ab1c16b726a839598801fe449f50f571
SG82_S122_L002_R1_001.fastq.gz	2829465	bb79264d542315772e824e7cd751244e
SG83_S130_L001_R1_001.fastq.gz	2572372	46e5297b8eef7b62ebfb4862b5e45f40
SG83_S130_L002_R1_001.fastq.gz	2555156	5ee5c697ff69eb2599588de2bfd61a8f
SG84_S138_L001_R1_001.fastq.gz	3648876	e565eb1318be061c53da6ebf9e360151
SG84_S138_L002_R1_001.fastq.gz	3633089	9cf34ce0b69df5a18e163bc394ba90a5
SG85_S52_L001_R1_001.fastq.gz	5171000	8604ebcf6f1f47c918976e64dba256d1
SG85_S52_L002_R1_001.fastq.gz	5157044	880ecf11f877e8306b397cf77703dee0
SG86_S60_L001_R1_001.fastq.gz	5098550	653845e6edabae3d043bece0d280cee2
SG86_S60_L002_R1_001.fastq.gz	5075843	e50d2aa911bc9bab76cd587f4007f91e
SG87_S68_L001_R1_001.fastq.gz	5247172	95fdcef76c52885eb81a04cb9cdb2614
SG87_S68_L002_R1_001.fastq.gz	5222394	11298dfabe210d96400126f4a570b1f2
SG88_S76_L001_R1_001.fastq.gz	3962188	ef1081efaaf196c2c60f4393cadf46d4
SG88_S76_L002_R1_001.fastq.gz	3957397	49dbac02246f7db1c0339f6f0d1f5e2a
SG89_S84_L001_R1_001.fastq.gz	3684741	340dfef7f5aa710d561e78ad24ef015f
SG89_S84_L002_R1_001.fastq.gz	3650623	609dbcd08939992463fc918cceb9d8b
SG8_S101_L001_R1_001.fastq.gz	3686028	633549fdb972933f68e925def25b2d24
SG8_S101_L002_R1_001.fastq.gz	3659952	9ca446d032e8c81d0427b1193d0c147e
SG90_S92_L001_R1_001.fastq.gz	3976209	37b19a46c91c1b138c0a3869f27d1b46

SG90_S92_L002_R1_001.fastq.gz	3941285	93ffff408a964c64de00e0447ae397df
SG91_S100_L001_R1_001.fastq.gz	3410003	dba2b32042b76bcc9a9f4ea926ba1130
SG91_S100_L002_R1_001.fastq.gz	3389845	2607e738ce92cc52247c33f420ff0264
SG93_S115_L001_R1_001.fastq.gz	3043653	56b6059d00352ad6ac731bc45e92d34b
SG93_S115_L002_R1_001.fastq.gz	3018680	36ad0e55f8d2adc256a807c5d0b1741f
SG94_S123_L001_R1_001.fastq.gz	3090917	a4968bbcb768930389842e3155cc0261
SG94_S123_L002_R1_001.fastq.gz	3082949	ac0f23656c0bbb29c423ecadf87ed398
SG95_S131_L001_R1_001.fastq.gz	2526894	9a37549e9ad876a5675d8022f054049d
SG95_S131_L002_R1_001.fastq.gz	2486044	6005f27c24038b1a1b00d958747d299d
SG96_S139_L001_R1_001.fastq.gz	2407972	297c28a7000a66bc04aede51f6cb1b29
SG96_S139_L002_R1_001.fastq.gz	2378077	3cfad2181cfc47729e9dc75d87058afd
SG97_S140_L001_R1_001.fastq.gz	4218056	92ac7c7f326c972ffc54ce6b2db05ff
SG97_S140_L002_R1_001.fastq.gz	4211641	71f16b19a96bc37e74db848229ed5d07
SG98_S144_L001_R1_001.fastq.gz	4519953	ece7025883c93c78e339986ac7538d56
SG98_S144_L002_R1_001.fastq.gz	4496963	e278cce9fc3bd184512a607af080508b
SG99_S148_L001_R1_001.fastq.gz	3496500	06cc5275fe713ce3d424c1d74772b579
SG99_S148_L002_R1_001.fastq.gz	3478748	f6f1912d1bd123d8982795c1905813bd
SG9_S108_L001_R1_001.fastq.gz	3245691	3035d75b3df085d65fb8da5a66727496
SG9_S108_L002_R1_001.fastq.gz	3224458	7a397c90ce6eff1def64f3748cd8c4c6